

BIAXIAL STRENGTH OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES USING FLAT TEST SPECIMENS *

Sven-Erik THOR

*The Aeronautical Research Institute of Sweden, FFA
S-161 11 Bromma, Sweden*

The biaxial behavior of fiber reinforced plastics can be studied with principally two different types of specimen configurations

- Tubular specimens
- Flat specimens

This paper describes the investigation of biaxial strength of graphite/epoxy laminates using flat test specimens.

The stacking geometries of the laminates were, $[0, \pm 45, 90]_{S8}$, $[0, 0, \pm 45]_{S8}$ and $[0, \pm 60]_{S6}$, manufactured from T300 Graphite/Narmco 5208 Epoxy.

The test results are compared with the Tsai - Hill failure theory.

* This work was sponsored by the Defence Materials Administration, Air Materials Department (FMV-F:FL), Stockholm.

INTRODUCTION

Biaxial tests on fiber reinforced plastics can be carried out on either flat or tubular specimens. Biaxial stress states can also be obtained in uniaxially loaded test specimens with off axis fiber orientation. The choice of test method is, however, somewhat difficult because it depends on what type of comparisons with an actual structure that should be done, see e.g. Refs. [1] - [3].

This paper describes a method for determining failure surfaces for flat test specimens loaded biaxially. The loads are introduced as a combination of tension (or compression) and shear. By using this method comparisons may be made with flat structures with free edges. This type of specimen is, compared to tubular specimens, relatively easy to manufacture and to reproduce.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Testing equipment

The test specimens are loaded in a test rig named "The Scissor". The special features of this load rig are illustrated in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Principle lay-out of testing equipment

- | | |
|------------------|--------------------|
| 1. Shear link | 5. Hinge |
| 2. — " — | 6. — " — |
| 3. Test specimen | 7. Scissor link |
| 4. Shear pins | 8. Hydraulic jack |
| | 9. Load transducer |

Figure 2. Loading rig

The load rig makes it possible to apply two independent load systems at the same time.

1. Tensile or compressive loads are applied with the hydraulic jack, no. 8 in Figure 2.
2. Shear loads are introduced through the shear links, nos. 1 and 2 in Figure 2.

The resulting stress state in the middle of the specimen will thus consist of mainly σ_x and τ_{xy} .

Effects near the free edges will be discussed later on.

Materials and test specimens

The experimental program involved three different laminate configurations: $[0, \pm 45, 90]_{S8}$, $[0, 0, \pm 45]_{S8}$ and $[0, \pm 60]_{S6}$. The laminates were cut with a diamond saw and machined to the dimensions of the test specimen, Figure 3. The ends of the specimen were reinforced with 3 mm aluminum tabs, bonded to the laminate with FM 123 adhesive.

Figure 3. Test specimen and dimensions

All loads were introduced in the specimen by means of 22 shear pins, 11 on each side. In order to avoid asymmetric loading the holes in the specimen were all reamed in the testing equipment.

Experimental procedure

In the present study, the test specimens were loaded until failure with different ratio between the tensile (or compressive) and shear loads. Table 1 shows the number of test specimens for the different ratios, Ref. [4].

Table 1. Number of test specimens

Laminate	Loading ratio F_x/F_{xy}						
	F_x	$-F_x$	F_{xy}	3/1	2/1	-3/1	-2/1
$[0, \pm 45, 90]_{S8}$	5	3	3	3	3	3	3
$[0, 0, \pm 45]_{S8}$	5	5	5	4	4	4	4
$[0, \pm 60]_{S6}$	5	5	5	4	4	4	4

F_x = Tensile load

$-F_x$ = Compressive load

F_{xy} = Shear load

The stresses are introduced by applying loads in the x and xy directions simultaneously while keeping the ratio of F_x/F_{xy} constant.

Experimental results

Table 2-4 shows the failure stress (σ, τ) and standard deviations (s_x, s_{xy}) for the different laminates and loading ratios.

Table 2. Failure stresses [N/mm^2], one load system

Laminate	Load type					
	F_x		$-F_x$		F_{xy}	
	σ_x	s_x	σ_x	s_x	τ_{xy}	s_{xy}
$[0, \pm 45, 90]_{S8}$	650	27	-436	41	374	14
$[0, 0, \pm 45]_{S8}$	871	56	-648	26	383	23
$[0, \pm 60]_{S6}$	680	21	-417	32	418	37

Table 3. Failure stresses [N/mm^2], tensile/shear loads

Laminate	Load type							
	3/1				2/1			
	σ_x	τ_{xy}	s_x	s_{xy}	σ_x	τ_{xy}	s_x	s_{xy}
$[0, \pm 45, 90]_{S8}$	502	181	30	16	411	202	43	18
$[0, 0, \pm 45]_{S8}$	793	264	40	13	624	315	16	8
$[0, \pm 60]_{S6}$	569	187	39	12	489	234	24	20

Table 4. Failure stresses [N/mm^2], compressive/shear loads

Laminate	Load type							
	-3/1				-2/1			
	σ_x	τ_{xy}	s_x	s_{xy}	σ_x	τ_{xy}	s_x	s_{xy}
$[0, \pm 45, 90]_{S8}$	-436	145	9	2	-412	197	66	31
$[0, 0, \pm 45]_{S8}$	-559	183	48	13	-532	262	52	33
$[0, \pm 60]_{S6}$	-423	138	46	15	-374	186	37	20

σ_x = Failure stress in x-direction N/mm^2
 τ_{xy} = - " - - " - " xy - " - - " -
 s_x = standard deviation in x-direction - " -
 s_{xy} = - " - - " - " xy - " - - " -

The above ratio corresponds to the actual ratio between the loads at the continuous loading, this ratio is not necessarily equal to the failure ratio due to the redistribution of loads at failure.

Figures 4-6 show the failure stresses in the $\sigma - \tau$ -plane, where the calculated failure envelope also has been drawn.

Figure 4. Failure stresses for laminate $[0, \pm 45, 90]_{S8}$

Figure 5. Failure stresses for laminate $[0, 0, \pm 45]_{S8}$

Figure 6. Failure stresses for laminate $[0, \pm 60]_{S6}$

COMPARISON WITH FAILURE CRITERION

Many different criteria have been proposed for failure of anisotropic materials under combined loading. Summaries are, for example, given in Refs. [5] and [6].

In the present investigation a modified Tsai-Hill criterion has been used. The criterion has the following form:

$$\varphi = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{F_1}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{\rho} \cdot \frac{\sigma_1 \cdot \sigma_2}{F_1 \cdot F_2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{F_{12}}\right)^2}$$

where σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} are the actual stresses in the principal material directions and F_1 , F_2 and F_{12} are the corresponding failure stresses. Failure of a single ply is assumed to occur when $\phi \geq 1$. The laminate fails when all plies have $\phi \geq 1$ or if fiber failure has occurred in any ply. ρ is an interaction factor which is determined from tests.

The Tsai-Hill failure criterion combined with a multilinear theory for the behavior of a laminate, [5] has been used in the comparison with the test results.

In this multilinear analysis the load is incremented until one of the layers has reached such a stress state that matrix failure occurs. When increasing the load beyond this point, it is assumed that the transverse (E_2) and shear (G_{12}) moduli is set equal to zero. This implies that the failed layer no longer can take loads in the transverse and shear directions.

The point where E_2 and G_{12} is set to zero, for the individual layers, is as mentioned above determined with the modified Tsai-Hill criterion. Fiber failure on the other hand is assumed to occur in one layer when the stress σ_1 in the fiber direction has reached the ultimate stress in this direction, F_1 . The failure criterion is thus only used for determining when matrix failure occurs.

Normally it is not possible to distinguish between fiber and matrix failure with the Tsai-Hill criterion. Matrix failure in a layer is, however, defined to occur when $\phi \geq 1$ and the ratio σ_2/F_2 or τ_{12}/F_{12} is the largest of the ratios under the square root, in the equation above.

These assumptions have been included in a computer program named PS 32, the program listing can be found in Ref. [5] part 2.

Results from PS 32 have been plotted in Figs. 4-6. Material data input to PS 32 has been obtained from tests with 25 mm wide and 200 mm long test coupons.

CONCLUSIONS

Comparisons between test results and failure criterion show good agreement, except in the second quadrant where the test results are lower than the computed ones. This comparison is made with the assumption that stresses in the test specimen are defined as applied load divided by area.

Local effects at free edges, however, results in local stresses in the middle of the specimen that are larger than the mean stresses in the laminate. Finite element calculations [2] and strain measurements [4] indicate that stresses in the middle can be a factor 1.1 to 2.0 greater than the mean stresses, for this type of test specimen. This indicates that this type of failure criterion is a safe estimate of the failure stresses for a laminate.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hahn, H.T. and Erikson, J.: Characterization of composite laminates using tubular specimens, AFML-TR-77-144.
- [2] Hällgren, I., et. al.: Development of a test method for determining strength characteristics of fiber-reinforced plastics at combined loading. FFA Report HU-1434. In Swedish.
- [3] Daniel, I.M.: Biaxial testing of graphite/epoxy composites containing stress concentrations, AFML-TR-76-244.
- [4] Thor, S.-E.: Verification of validity of failure criteria for fiber-reinforced plastics. Part I-III, FFA Reports HU-1816, HU-2041, HU-2123. In Swedish.

- [5] Stehlin, P.: Non-linear strain response of fibre reinforced plastic laminates. FFA Report HU-1716:0, Part 1 and 2.
- [6] Jones, R.M. and Hennemann, C.F.: Biaxial strength characteristics of fiber-reinforced composite laminae, in ICCM 2.